

Economic burden of vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile and head & neck cancers in Bulgaria

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Received 10 September 2024 ♦ Accepted 18 September 2024 ♦ Published 16 October 2024

Citation: Lebanova H, Petrova E, Stoev S (2024) Economic burden of vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile and head & neck cancers in Bulgaria. *Pharmacia* 71: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e136772>

Abstract

A retrospective, cost-of-illness study aimed at identifying direct healthcare costs of vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile, and H&N cancers in Bulgaria from the payer perspective and calculating indirect costs and the associated years of life lost was carried out. Costs' data were obtained from the National Health Insurance Fund from January 2018 to December 2020. Years of life lost were calculated based on the country and gender-specific life expectancy. The human capital approach was used to evaluate the indirect costs. The total treatment costs for 3623 patients were EUR 10,875,771 (2018), EUR 11,922,521 (2019) and EUR 12,329,463 (2020). The costs associated with radiotherapy and drug acquisition and administration accounted for the majority (75–78%) of total healthcare costs. A cumulative loss of approximately 33,299 life years occurred between 2018 and 2020. The costs of productivity losses were estimated at EUR 14,113,265.

Keywords

economic burden, cost of illness, HPV-related cancers, HPV, direct costs, years of life lost

Introduction

HPV (Human papillomavirus) infection is now recognized as the most prevalent sexually transmitted disease worldwide (Winer and Koutsky 2004; Liu et al. 2015).

HPV is a group of more than 200 related viruses. HPV types fall into two groups, low-risk and high-risk. Low-risk HPVs mostly cause no disease. However, a few low-risk HPV types can cause warts on or around the genitals, anus, mouth, or throat. High-risk HPVs are proven to be oncogenic and can cause several types of cancer. There are about 14 high-risk HPV types including HPV 16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 56, 58, 59, 66, and 68. Two of these, HPV16 and HPV18, are responsible for most HPV-related cancers (PDQ Screening and Prevention Editorial Board 2014).

The correlation between oncogenic HPV strains and their ability to cause cancer has initially been proven for cervical cancer (Burd 2003). Cervical cancer is the most common type of cancer associated with HPV globally, with over half a million cases reported annually (Sung et al. 2021).

Associated with HPV are the cancers of cervix (WHO ICD 10th revision code C53), vagina (ICD 10 C52), vulva (ICD 10 C51), penis (ICD 10 C60), anus (ICD 10 C21), oral cavity and lip (ICD 10 C00–C06), nasopharynx (ICD 10 C11), oropharynx (ICD 10 C09–C10), hypopharynx (ICD 10 C12–C13) and larynx (ICD 10 C32) (Pešut et al. 2021).

HPV is involved in one of at least 2 pathways leading to vulvar squamous cell carcinoma (VSCC). The percentage of HPV-positive VSCCs ranges from 18% to 75%, depending on the geographical area (Rakislova et al. 2017). HPV-related tumors affect relatively young women, typically in their

working years, and arise from high-grade intraepithelial lesions, identical to other HPV-associated premalignant lesions of the anogenital tract (Van Der Avoort et al. 2006). HPV-independent tumors tend to affect older women and usually arise in a background of inflammatory skin disorders and a subtle variant of in situ lesion called differentiated vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia (Van Der Avoort et al. 2006). HPV-positive tumors tend to be of basaloid or warty types, whereas HPV-independent tumors tend to be of keratinizing type, but there is frequent overlap between histologic types (Eva et al. 2020). There is no conclusive evidence yet on the best strategy in terms of determining HPV attribution. Currently, there are no differences in treatment between HPV-associated and HPV-independent VSCC, but novel immunological strategies based on anti-HPV antigens are being evaluated in clinical trials (Rakislova et al. 2017). The majority of vulvar cancers (25–40%) are caused by HPV (De Sanjosé et al. 2013; de Sanjose et al. 2018).

Primary vaginal cancer is rare, constituting only 1%–2% of all female genital tract malignancies and only 10% of all vaginal malignant neoplasms (Adhikari et al. 2017). Historically, these cancers are more common in elderly and postmenopausal women. If vaginal malignancy is found in younger women, it is usually etiologically linked to cervical cancer, specifically with regard to the persistence of high-risk HPV infections (Hellman et al. 2004). Vaginal cancers, although rare, are increasingly being seen in younger women owing to the increase in persistent high-risk HPV infections, especially in settings with a high HIV prevalence (Adams et al. 2021). As with premalignant cervical lesions and carcinoma of the cervix, persistent HPV infection, particularly the HPV 16 subtype, has been associated with the long-term development of high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesion (HSIL) and carcinoma of the vagina (Hampl et al. 2006; Serrano et al. 2015; Lamos et al. 2016). The introduction of HPV vaccination as a primary prevention strategy for cervical cancer has also been shown to reduce the prevalence of noncervical premalignant lesions among vaccinated women (Garland et al. 2016). Long-term trend analyses from the Norwegian Cancer Register also show promising estimates of a reduction in HPV-associated cases of vaginal cancer in future years among HPV-vaccinated communities (Hansen et al. 2018). There is no evidence to indicate routine screening for vaginal cancer after hysterectomy for benign disease. If a hysterectomy has been performed for persistent HSIL after repeated excisional procedures of the cervix, vault smears and colposcopy are recommended for long-term follow-up (Videlefsky et al. 2000; Farghaly et al. 2006). In those cases where screening for vaginal cancer is indicated, HPV tests adequately correlate with cytological findings (Bansal et al. 2011). Independently of that, co-testing seems to offer better accuracy in the diagnosis of recurrent disease- as observed during follow-up after treatment of premalignant cervical lesions (Hui et al. 2016). Most vaginal cancers (75%) are caused by HPV (INSTITUTE 2022).

Anal cancer is a rare malignancy with increasing incidence, notably in women. This disease is highly associated

with HPV infection and its incidence and mortality are currently rising (Lum et al. 2020). In fact, women with a history of cervical cancer (or pre-cancer) have an increased risk of anal cancer (INSTITUTE 2022). Most patients present with localized disease which has a high survival after definitive treatment with chemoradiation. For patients who develop metastatic disease or present with this de novo, survival is poor. HPV vaccination is expected to reduce the development of (pre)malignant anal lesions (Hui et al. 2016).

Penile cancer is an aggressive disease with a poor prognosis in advanced stages (Thomas et al. 2021). In penile carcinogenesis, two major pathways are known. Besides a non-human papillomavirus (HPV)-related pathway (mainly caused by phimosis and chronic inflammation), up to 50% of penile carcinomas are HPV-related (HPV high-risk types) (Thomas et al. 2021).

The reported worldwide prevalence of HPV-associated head and neck cancers (H&NCs) varies between 25.9 and 30% (Sastre-Garau and Harlé 2020; Agelaki et al. 2024). The frequency of HPV association is different according to tumor localizations. The highest rate (35%) is observed for tumors located in the oropharynx, particularly when developed in lymphoepithelial sites such as the palatine tonsil (56 to 62%) and the base of the tongue (40%). Lower rates are observed in tumors developed in the oral cavity, (5.8 to 23.5%), in the larynx (3.3 to 24.0%), or in the soft palate (3.1%). There is a striking geographic heterogeneity of HPV prevalence in oropharyngeal tumors: rates are higher in the United States (59.3%) and in Europe (31.1%) than in Brazil (4.1%) (Sastre-Garau and Harlé 2020). In the United States, an increase in the prevalence of H&NCs was observed between 1984–1989 and 2000–2004, rising from 16.3 to 71.7% (Sastre-Garau and Harlé 2020). A significant increase in HPV-related tumors developed in women has also been observed in France (Sastre-Garau and Harlé 2020). There is a lack of data on the prevalence of vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile, and head and neck cancers in Bulgaria.

HPV-related malignancies and illnesses impose a significant financial burden on healthcare systems worldwide (Borget et al. 2011; Baio et al. 2012; Chesson et al. 2012; Préaud and LARGERON 2013; Ki et al. 2018). Most expenditures are related to hospital care and are concentrated in the first year of care (Abramowitz et al. 2018; Saxena et al. 2022). Data on the economic burden of HPV-related cancers in Bulgaria is scarce. A previous retrospective study estimated that direct and indirect costs associated with cervical cancer in Bulgaria for three years amount to up to € 26 M (Lebanova et al. 2023). A model developed for nine Central Eastern European Countries estimates the number of HPV-related deaths and years of life lost in 2019 based on published HPV-attributable fractions. According to the results, the present value of the future lost productivity in Bulgaria due to cervical, anal, pharynx and larynx cancers is € 7 M (Sabale et al. 2024).

The current study aims to identify direct healthcare costs of vaginal, vulvar, anal, penile, and H&N cancers

in Bulgaria and to calculate indirect costs and years of life lost associated with vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile and head&neck cancers.

Methods

Study population

The study includes patients diagnosed with vulvar (ICD 10 C51), vaginal (ICD 10 C52), anal (ICD 10 C21), penile (ICD 10 C60) and H&N cancers - hypopharynx, larynx, nasopharynx, oral cavity, oropharynx (ICD 10 (C01 – C06; C09–C13; C32) in Bulgaria.

Direct costs

A prevalence-based, non-interventional cost of illness study was conducted based on data sourced from Bulgarian national databases and registries. The aggregated cost information was collected from the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) database without having access to individual patient-level information. Data was obtained based on ICD-10 codes without any personal identifiers such as initials, age, city, etc.

Direct costs in the study include drug costs and healthcare resources costs for inpatient and outpatient care services related to the treatment and follow-up of patients with HPV-related cancers of interest. Publicly available and officially requested data for vaginal, vulvar, penile, anal and H&N cancers management in Bulgaria was extracted from the NHIF (NHIF 2022). It provides information on the number of patients (by ICD-code), respective treatment, hospitalizations (by clinical pathway), and treatment costs (hospitalization, drug therapy, laboratory tests, ambulatory procedures, ambulatory visits, etc.). Data include primary care services, ambulatory health services, laboratory and imaging, hospitalization, treatments (chemotherapy, radiotherapy, brachytherapy, and palliation), clinical pathways, and the prevalence of vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile and head&neck cancers. The clinical pathway is defined in the Bulgarian legislation as a system of requirements and guidelines for the behavior of different health professionals during diagnostic and treatment procedures of patients requiring hospitalization. Each hospitalization in the Bulgarian healthcare system is valued and paid to the provider according to the amount pre-set for the relevant clinical pathway.

The number of healthcare resources used associated with vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile and head&neck cancers treatment per year was collected for the respective ICD-10 code (C01–C06; C09–C13; C21; C32; C51; C52; C60) and costed based on local tariffs within the National Framework Agreement 2020–2022 (National Health Insurance Fund 2020). All identifiable costs are included in the estimate and were converted from Bulgarian lev (BGN) to Euro (EUR) using the fixed exchange rate of the Bulgarian National Bank (EUR 1 = 1.95583 BGN since 5 July 1997)

(Anon 2016). All direct costs were estimated from the Bulgarian healthcare-payer perspective.

Indirect costs

Country- and gender-specific life expectancy were sourced from the National Statistical Institute (National Statistical Institute 2022). The years of life lost at the country level were calculated by summing the number of vaginal, vulvar, penile, anal, and H&N cancers-specific deaths for a given age multiplied by the expected life years remaining at the mid-point for each age. The years of working life lost due to premature death from vaginal, vulvar, penile, anal, and H&N cancers were calculated by subtracting the age at death from the retirement age of 61 years for women and 64 years for men. Years of life lost and years of working life lost were calculated for each age and then summed up. The number of deaths up to 61/64 years of age was then multiplied by the Gross Domestic Product per employed individual- current prices for the respective year and lost GDP per year were calculated. The human capital approach was used to estimate the indirect costs due to productivity loss. Lost productivity was defined as productivity loss as % of GDP incurred to society due to cancer-specific premature mortality.

Data analysis

A cost calculator was designed in Excel to integrate all direct costs of treatment of vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile, and H&N cancers. Data was collected and analyzed for each calendar year in the time period between 2018 and 2020. Data provided by the National Health Insurance Fund on drug therapy, inpatient, and outpatient costs were divided into categories (drug acquisition and administration costs, inpatient and outpatient health care utilization (HCRU) costs) and were presented as a total healthcare cost for each year. Data is analyzed and presented using descriptive statistics. The proportions of deaths up to 61 years of age for females and 64 years of age for males were compared by using a *t*-test for two proportions. The results were considered significant when *p*-values were less than 0.05. MS Office package (2019) as well as add-ons and SPSS v.22 were used.

Study sample

The study consisted of the total number of patients diagnosed with vaginal, vulvar, penile, anal, and H&N cancers (ICD 10 C01–C06; C09–C13; C21; C32; C51; C52; C60) on treatment for the period 2018–2020 indexed in the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) database. The number of patients who received inpatient treatment during the study period was consistent across the years with a slight decrease in 2020 (Table 1). The most prevalent cancers among the sample size were larynx (C32), nasopharynx cancer (C11) and tongue cancer (C01 & C02). However, the biggest decrease in the number of cases is observed in

Table 1. Study sample.

ICD-10 Code	2018 (N)	2019 (N)	2020 (N)
C01	40	37	33
C02	128	113	114
C03	34	31	39
C04	79	77	83
C05	31	34	26
C06	27	27	31
C09	92	108	123
C10	83	94	99
C11	140	130	99
C12	0	3	0
C13	94	110	110
C21	61	55	47
C32	312	288	255
C51	65	62	58
C52	29	27	22
C60	27	22	24
Total	1242	1218	1163

Source: National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF), data on file.

nasopharynx cancer (-29% 2018 vs 2020) and anal cancer (-23% 2018 vs 2019). The largest increase in the number of cases is recorded for tonsil cancer (+34% 2018 vs 2019).

Results

Direct costs

Drug acquisition costs

The cumulative drug acquisition costs for the study period amounted to 11 139 623 euros. The highest drug acquisition costs were observed in the C32 population – 3 096 198 euros for the study horizon, followed by the C09 population (Table 2). There has been a notable increase in annual expenditures – from 2.78 million euro in 2018 to 4.34 million euro in 2020.

Table 2. Drug acquisition costs 2018–2020.

ICD 10 Code	2018	2019	2020	Total
C01	93 207 €	97 474 €	128 954 €	319 635 €
C02	324 997 €	425 944 €	391 595 €	1 142 536 €
C03	71 051 €	94 670 €	165 011 €	330 732 €
C04	171 718 €	154 090 €	183 679 €	509 487 €
C05	87 190 €	136 881 €	91 740 €	315 811 €
C06	53 229 €	123 942 €	120 992 €	298 164 €
C09	350 913 €	613 023 €	738 737 €	1 702 673 €
C10	228 687 €	464 390 €	395 965 €	1 089 042 €
C12	- €	- €	- €	- €
C11	347 585 €	435 261 €	311 429 €	1 094 274 €
C13	250 570 €	293 761 €	496 096 €	1 040 427 €
C21	24 619 €	26 645 €	28 077 €	79 341 €
C32	747 077 €	1 092 423 €	1 256 698 €	3 096 198 €
C51	9 284 €	20 498 €	15 600 €	45 382 €
C52	10 065 €	17 964 €	13 684 €	41 713 €
C60	15 687 €	13 613 €	4 908 €	34 208 €
Total	2 785 878 €	4 010 580 €	4 343 165 €	11 139 623 €

Source: National Health Insurance Fund.

Fig. 1 shows the distribution of drug acquisition costs, with the lowest costs for tonsil, penile, and vaginal cancers. These findings align with the group with the fewest patients receiving treatment.

Figure 1. Distribution of drug acquisition costs by ICD-10 diagnosis. Source: National Health Insurance Fund

Drug administration costs

Drug administration costs were identified through the clinical pathway P240 “Long-term systemic parenteral drug treatment of malignant solid tumors and related complications” (Table 3). The drug administration costs for the study time horizon were estimated at 1 480 533 €, representing 18%, 13% and 10% of the total drug acquisition costs for 2018, 2019 and 2020, respectively.

Table 3. Drug administration costs.

CP#	Description	2018	2019	2020
Costs (€)				
P240	Long-term systemic parenteral drug treatment of malignant solid tumors and related complications	505 847	518 823	455 863
Patients (N)				
P240	Long-term systemic parenteral drug treatment of malignant solid tumors and related complications	623	610	554

Source: National Health Insurance Fund; CP – clinical pathway.

Inpatient costs

Inpatient costs in our study consisted of diagnosing and staging costs, radiotherapy costs, radiosurgery costs, surgical treatment and palliative care costs. Relevant costs were extracted through the respective clinical pathways presented in Suppl. material 1: table S1. Diagnosis and staging costs were identified through clinical pathways P241.1 and P241.2 (for 2018&2019) and P241.3 and P241.5 (for 2020). Scintigraphy, PET/CT and SPECT/CT costs were also included in this category. Radiotherapy costs were identified through 7 clinical pathways – P246, P248, P249, P250.1, P250.2, P251.1 and P251.2. The total

radiotherapy costs were €14 420 852. Surgical treatment costs were identified through the respective clinical pathways for different cancers and were estimated at a total of €4 192 649. The total costs of palliative care during the study period were 100 euro in 2018. In 2019 and 2020, the NHIF did not report any costs in this category. The low palliative care costs are largely due to the high level of out-of-pocket expenditure in this category. Radiotherapy accounts for the largest proportion (65–68%) of inpatient costs. The share of the cost categories for in-patient care remained stable (Table 4).

Table 4. Inpatient costs.

	2018	2019	2020
Total inpatient costs	7 353 004 €	7 152 636 €	7 331 431 €
Diagnosis and staging costs	994 580 €	1 056 390 €	1 080 468 €
Radiotherapy	4 964 409 €	4 616 674 €	4 839 768 €
Radiosurgery	29 911 €	39 114 €	23 008 €
Palliative care	100 €	- €	- €
Surgical treatment	1 364 005 €	1 440 458 €	1 388 186 €

Source: National Health Insurance Fund.

Outpatient follow-up

The study also highlighted the expenses associated with outpatient follow-up. The analysis includes the cost of outpatient visits during the study period, as shown in Table 5. The considerable decrease observed in the number of outpatient visits in 2020 was possibly influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic and the restricted access to primary healthcare services.

Total direct costs

The specific expenditures related to anal, penile, vaginal, vulvar, and head and neck cancers in Bulgaria vary from €10,875,771 in 2018 to €12,329,463 in 2020, as shown in Table 6. The main reason for the observed increase is the significant amount of expenses related to drug acquisition.

Table 6. Total healthcare costs of vaginal, vulvar, penile, anal and H&N cancers (2018–2020).

	Direct costs (€)		
	2018	2019	2020
Drug acquisition costs	2 785 878 €	4 010 580 €	4 343 165 €
Drug administration costs	505 847 €	518 823 €	455 863 €
Diagnosing and staging costs	994 580 €	1 056 390 €	1 080 468 €
Radiotherapy	4 964 409 €	4 616 674 €	4 839 768 €
Surgical treatment	1 393 915 €	1 479 572 €	1 411 194 €
Palliative care	100 €	- €	- €
Outpatient follow-up	231 043 €	240 481 €	199 005 €
Total	10 875 771 €	11 922 521 €	12 329 463 €

The largest share of direct costs is attributed to radiotherapy (around 40%) followed by drug acquisition and administration costs. The majority of the remaining cost categories remain unchanged (Fig. 2).

Years of life lost and indirect costs

The human capital approach was used to measure the indirect costs related to the loss in productivity. Table 7 indicates that the mortality rates for H&N, vulvar, penile, anal, and vaginal cancers remained consistent at 749 deaths in 2018, 751 deaths in 2019, and 751 deaths in 2020. Comparing 2020 to 2018, there was a significant increase of 22% in the number of fatalities among females up to 61 years old and males up to 64 years old (250 deaths in 2018 vs. 321 deaths in 2020, $p < 0.05$). The majority of deaths are in males - between 80% and 83% (620 in 2018, 606 in 2019 and 601 in 2020 respectively) (Suppl. material 1: table S2).

For the study period, a total of 33299,40 years of life were lost (11273,41 in 2018, 11127,21 in 2019 and 10898,78 in 2020) – 26 241,17 for males and 7058,24 for females. A significant increase was observed in the years of working life lost in women – from 295 in 2018 to 432 in 2020

Table 5. Outpatient follow-up costs.

ICD 10	2018			2019			2020		
	N	patients	cost (EUR)	N	patients	cost (EUR)	N	Patients	cost (EUR)
C01	53	40	3523	43	32	2858	35	28	2326
C02	171	132	11366	216	159	14357	221	150	14689
C03	59	37	3922	69	45	4586	38	32	2526
C04	79	61	5251	111	72	7378	114	81	7577
C05	80	57	5317	101	72	6713	87	56	5783
C06	55	39	3656	61	45	4055	49	38	3257
C09	139	92	9239	195	130	12961	170	117	11300
C10	60	43	3988	92	56	6115	78	55	5184
C11	244	181	16218	210	168	13958	199	153	13227
C12	1	1	66	3	2	199	2	2	133
C13	83	57	5517	96	65	6381	81	57	5384
C21	145	106	9638	172	121	11432	140	109	9306
C32	1690	1255	112331	1644	1239	109273	1287	997	85544
C51	364	250	24194	367	255	24394	288	212	19143
C52	135	85	8973	118	76	7843	95	67	6314
C60	118	87	7843	120	86	7976	110	81	7311
Total			231042 €			240481 €			199005 €

Source: National Health Insurance Fund.

Figure 2. Distribution of healthcare costs among categories (2018–2020).

Table 7. Total number of deaths (2018–2020).

ICD 10 code	2018			2019			2020		
	Total deaths	Deaths 18–64 men	Deaths 18–61 women	Total deaths	Deaths 18–64 men	Deaths 18–61 women	Total deaths	Deaths 18–64 men	Deaths 18–61 women
C01 - Malignant neoplasm of base of tongue	27	17	1	27	9	0	20	7	0
C02 - Malignant neoplasm of other and unspecified parts of the tongue	63	34	3	62	24	8	46	19	2
C03 - Malignant neoplasm of gum	10	3	0	9	3	0	11	3	2
C04 - Malignant neoplasm of floor of mouth	24	11	2	16	12	0	31	13	12
C05 - Malignant neoplasm of the palate	12	4	0	14	6	1	18	6	1
C06 - Malignant neoplasm of other and unspecified parts of mouth	16	4	0	30	12	1	35	8	4
C09 - Malignant neoplasm of the tonsil	24	9	2	29	13	2	29	13	2
C10 - Malignant neoplasm of oropharynx	27	15	3	33	15	2	28	11	2
C11 - Malignant neoplasm of nasopharynx	52	16	5	46	17	8	30	16	3
C12 - Malignant neoplasm of piriform sinus	4	1	0	2	0	0	6	0	0
C13 - Malignant neoplasm of hypopharynx	40	10	2	43	20	0	39	16	0
C21 - Malignant neoplasm of the anus and anal canal	22	3	0	21	4	4	17	2	2
C32 - Malignant neoplasm of larynx	353	83	6	351	133	8	373	150	8
C51 - Malignant neoplasm of the vulva	35	0	7	42	0	5	36	0	7
C52 - Malignant neoplasm of the vagina (vagina)	13	0	2	9	0	1	14	0	4
C60 - Malignant neoplasm of the penis	27	7	0	17	5	0	18	8	0
Total	749	217	33	751	273	40	751	272	49

(Table 8). The majority of years of life lost were recorded in larynx cancer (C32) and tongue cancer (C01&C02).

The indirect costs associated with productivity losses range from €3 391 308 to €5 124 840 per year based on the lost gross domestic product (GDP) per employed person (Table 9).

Discussion

HPV plays a pivotal role in the etiology of various cancers, including vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile, and head and neck (H&N) cancers (PDQ Screening and Prevention Editorial Board 2014). Nevertheless, HPV vaccination possesses the

capacity to reduce the incidence of these diseases and the corresponding economic strain, respectively (Hartwig et al. 2015). Currently, the 9-valent HPV vaccine is indicated for prevention of HPV-related head and neck cancers in the US and Canada, but not in Europe (Anon 2023).

The economic burden associated with these HPV-related cancers is substantial, encompassing direct medical costs and indirect costs. Data from the NHIF database indicate that the overall costs (medicines, hospitalizations, outpatient, diagnostic) due to these cancers represent a significant burden on the Bulgarian healthcare system, totaling more than 12 million euros per year, or 0.25% of the total NHIF budget. Due to reimbursement of new medicines, the cost of drug therapy doubles over the period.

Table 8. Years of life lost stratified by type of cancer.

ICD-10 code	2018				2019				2020			
	YLLs		WYLLs		YLLs		WYLLs		YLLs		WYLLs	
	male	female	male	female	male	female	male	female	male	female	male	female
C01 - Malignant neoplasm of base of tongue	409,73	34,29	107,00	4,00	340,03	28,22	54,00	0,00	289,20	6,19	105,00	0,00
C02 - Malignant neoplasm of other and unspecified parts of the tongue	930,95	214,66	345,00	44,00	722,40	335,89	177,00	99,00	525,58	173,28	167,00	18,00
C03 - Malignant neoplasm of gum	118,88	25,48	28,00	0,00	125,27	0,00	26,00	0,00	88,89	89,07	43,00	13,00
C04 - Malignant neoplasm of floor of mouth	364,16	97,05	114,00	32,00	296,50	0,00	117,00	0,00	416,30	572,18	148,00	111,00
C05 - Malignant neoplasm of the palate	165,65	11,22	37,00	0,00	140,36	56,24	29,00	8,00	153,85	86,24	23,00	2,00
C06 - Malignant neoplasm of other and unspecified parts of mouth	233,54	3,72	56,00	0,00	346,62	86,60	80,00	11,00	242,40	267,98	69,00	45,00
C09 - Malignant neoplasm of the tonsil	345,87	66,77	87,00	28,00	404,53	84,12	91,00	24,00	353,25	118,01	141,00	20,00
C10 - Malignant neoplasm of oropharynx	475,40	110,51	230,00	19,00	475,14	106,14	171,00	16,00	312,88	83,85	100,00	1,00
C11 - Malignant neoplasm of nasopharynx	686,22	231,09	194,00	65,00	501,16	312,25	179,00	89,00	396,80	154,65	184,00	18,00
C12 - Malignant neoplasm of piriform sinus	44,23	16,36	6,00	0,00	10,08	5,60	0,00	0,00	28,01	32,64	0,00	0,00
C13 - Malignant neoplasm of hypopharynx	511,25	78,74	71,00	33,00	594,49	50,14	183,00	0,00	497,32	20,66	122,00	0,00
C21 - Malignant neoplasm of the anus and anal canal	144,53	114,44	24,00	0,00	139,51	212,56	51,00	43,00	113,40	101,65	40,00	14,00
C32 - Malignant neoplasm of larynx	4528,78	362,01	803,00	37,00	4480,73	436,65	945,00	67,00	4505,04	375,61	1051,00	58,00
C51 - Malignant neoplasm of the vulva	0,00	407,34	0,00	25,00	0,00	525,33	0,00	32,00	0,00	427,20	0,00	72,00
C52 - Malignant neoplasm of the vagina (vagina)	0,00	182,82	0,00	8,00	0,00	127,57	0,00	10,00	0,00	225,23	0,00	59,00
C60 - Malignant neoplasm of the penis	357,72	0,00	77,00	0,00	183,10	0,00	33,00	0,00	241,42	0,00	118,00	0,00
Total	9316,91	1956,50	2179,00	295,00	8759,92	2367,30	2136,00	399,00	8164,34	2734,44	2311,00	431,00

Table 9. Indirect costs due to productivity loss.

	2018	2019	2020
N of all deaths due to the investigated malignancies (all ages)	749	751	751
N deaths male	620	606	601
N of deaths female	129	145	150
N of deaths up to 64 years of age (males)	217	273	272
N of deaths up to 61 years of age (females)	33	40	49
Years of life lost (male)	9317	8760	8164
Years of life lost (female)	1957	2367	2734
Mean YLL per male	15.03	14.46	13.58
Mean YLL per female	15.17	16.33	18.23
Years of working life lost (male)	2179	2136	2311
Years of working life lost (female)	295	399	431
Mean years of working life lost per male	10.04	7.82	8.50
Mean years of working life lost per female	8.94	9.98	8.80
GDP per employed—current prices (EUR) *	EUR 15 965	EUR 17420.61	EUR 17 768
Lost GDP (not produced GDP), EUR per year	EUR 3 991 308	EUR 4 997 118	EUR 5 124 840

* National Statistical Institute.

Cumulative direct costs of vaginal, vulvar, anal, penile and H&N cancers amount to 35 million euro for 2018–2020. Considering the share of HPV-related cancers in this group, a significant share of it could be attributed to HPV oncogenicity (Hartwig et al. 2015).

If we take into consideration the direct costs observed in our previous study of the economic burden of cervical cancer in Bulgaria and capture the cumulative direct costs for all HPV-related cancers the value increases significantly to 51.3 million euros for the period 2018–2020 (Lebanova et al. 2023). The findings indicate a consistent pattern of a rising number of deaths among individuals of working age, particularly in males. Additionally, the proportion of working-age deaths in relation to the total number of died patients with the examined malignancies remained stable throughout the study period for both genders. Consequently, the mean years of life lost (YLL) per individual is increasing each year of interest, which

contributes to the growing indirect costs of the analyzed HPV-associated oncology disorders. It is important to consider these results in the context of the fact that these highly fatal conditions can be mostly avoided by implementing long-lasting public health preventive programs that prioritize early screening and immunization against HPV infection, particularly for cervical, vaginal, vulvar and anal cancers (Giannone et al. 2022). This is because the known pathogenicity of these conditions is most commonly caused by HPV infection (De Martel et al. 2015; Hartwig et al. 2015). These results provide significant information for policymakers, such as helping them prioritize public health policies. This includes implementing programs to increase society's knowledge of the benefits of early screening and improving HPV vaccination coverage.

Currently, the HPV vaccine is recommended and fully funded by the Bulgarian Government for girls 12–13 years (Ministry of Health 2021). In 2021 the cohort was extended to ages 10–13 (Ministry of Health 2021). The set vaccination coverage rate of 75% was never achieved with vaccination coverage rates (VCR) for the last 6 years below 10% (Ministry of Health 2021). Real-world evidence demonstrates that HPV vaccination contributes to a decrease in the incidence of cervical cancer (Guo et al. 2018; Luostarinen et al. 2018; Lei et al. 2020; Kjaer et al. 2021; Mix et al. 2021), cervical, vulvar, vaginal and anal precancerous lesions (The Kirby Institute (University of NSW) 2012; Dehlendorf et al. 2018; Palmer et al. 2019; Innes et al. 2020; Johnson Jones et al. 2020; Racey et al. 2020; Shiko et al. 2020; Thamsborg et al. 2020; Verdoodt et al. 2020; Acuti Martellucci et al. 2021), anogenital warts (The Kirby Institute 2012; Dominiak-Felden et al. 2015; Herweijer et al. 2016; Thöne et al. 2017; Heard et al. 2017; Lutgendorf et al. 2017; Navarro-Illana et al. 2017; Checchi et al. 2019; Cocchio et al. 2020; Kumar et al. 2020; Orumaa et al. 2020; Tyros et al. 2021; Malheiro et al. 2024), and the prevalence of HPV infection (Deleré et al. 2014; Arbyn et al. 2016; Carozzi et al. 2018; Basu et al. 2019; Brotherton et al. 2019; Latsuzbaia et al. 2019; Olsson et al. 2020; Sekine et al.

2020; Lynge et al. 2020; Markowitz et al. 2020; Baussano et al. 2021; Jeannot et al. 2023). An adequate and sustainable rate of HPV vaccination will decrease the burden and costs of HPV-related cancers over time.

Our work prioritizes the urgent need to dedicate resources to national projects focused on mitigating the health and economic consequences of HPV-related cancers. Allocating resources to interventions targeting non-cervical HPV-associated cancers, a form of malignant tumors, not only helps alleviate the social and economic impact but also holds the potential for substantial economic gains in the near future, as indicated by above-mentioned data on premature mortality and years of life lost (YLL).

Cancers significantly impair the economic success of countries (Insinga et al. 2005). However, a thorough examination of the country-specific economic consequences of malignancies due to the modalities of national policies on screening programmes and social attitudes towards HPV vaccination is needed. A decision-analytic model incorporating economic feedback to assess the health consequences of HPV-caused cancers in relation to labor force and investment in prevention strategies would be considered, especially in low-income countries where health budgets are very limited.

The calculated economic burden of HPV-related malignancies in Bulgaria from 2018 to 2020 amounts to 51.3 million euros. This computation is derived from a recent study that analyzed the economic impact of cervical cancer, the most common complication of sexually transmitted HPV infections (Lebanova et al. 2023), along with the aforementioned current results. This estimation includes the direct costs associated with diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up, as well as the indirect costs related to years of life lost. This figure represents a yearly portion of 7.89% of the Bulgarian Gross Domestic Product recorded in 2020 (Anon 2011). These findings indicate that there is a need for nationwide actions to reduce the ongoing consequences of cancer, including neoplasms related to HPV. At least, additional resources should be allocated to areas where an approved vaccine approach is accessible, as it provides protection against HPV-related diseases like cervical, vaginal, vulvar, and anal malignancies.

Limitations

Our study has several limitations that merit acknowledgment. First, data on costs is provided by the Bulgarian National Health Insurance Fund which provides data from the public sector only. The results do not include out-of-

pocket patients' costs for outpatient visits, diagnostic tests, and follow-ups which are suspected to be considerable. This makes our estimates conservative as the true economic burden of vulvar, vaginal, anal, penile and head&neck cancers in Bulgaria is expected to be even higher.

Second, it is impossible to measure the effect of COVID-19 on vaginal, vulvar, penile, anal, and H&N cancers-related deaths in 2020 so it may be suspected that the years of life and productivity lost in 2020 are overestimated. Third, the above analyses were performed considering the fact that it is not possible to estimate with high certainty the HPV-attributable proportion of each of the health outcomes we assessed in the current study.

Despite these limitations, the current study provides a real-world update of the annual costs of diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up of HPV-associated malignancies. Current estimates of potentially vaccine-preventable HPV-associated cancers highlight the substantial economic burden of HPV infection and defend the potential of HPV vaccination to reduce the economic, medical, and social consequences of HPV.

Conclusion

The economic burden of vaginal, vulvar, penile, anal, and H&N cancers in Bulgaria is considerable and primarily driven by medicines and radiotherapy costs. The findings of our study suggest that it is essential to implement effective nationwide measures to mitigate the persistent effects of HPV-related cancers. It is necessary to commit more resources and focus on prevention, early diagnosis, and higher HPV vaccination coverage rates that potentially contribute to lower costs.

Funding

This study was funded by MSD Bulgaria. The funding sponsor approved the design of the study and the final version of the manuscript. The sponsor had no role in the collection, analysis, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript; or in the decision to publish the results.

Ethical approval

The current study has obtained approval from the Ethics Committee for Clinical Trials (Ministry of Health, Republic of Bulgaria) as a non-interventional cost-of illness study (notification letter # ECCT-5569/13.12.2023).

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Supplementary material 1

Additional information

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Data type: docx

Explanation note: table S1: Inpatient costs by categories; table S2: Distribution of deaths by sex.

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e136772.suppl1>